

MECHANISMS AND MODELS FOR DELAMINATION IN THE PRESENCE OF THROUGH-THICKNESS REINFORCEMENT

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SUMMARY: Prior detailed microscopic observations have revealed the essential mechanisms of damage in through-thickness reinforcing tows when a delamination crack passes. As expected, the damage sequence depends quite strongly on whether the crack is loaded in Mode I or Mode II and, if loading is mixed mode, the order of loading. Here, micromechanical models are presented that show how geometry and constituent material properties affect the deformation and displacement of a bridging tow. From these models, the effective bridging law for a bridged crack model of the delamination can be derived. An analytical model is presented that predicts the relationship between the crack displacement vector (mode I and Mode II displacements) and the bridging traction vector that acts on the fracture surfaces. Criteria for rupture or pullout of the bridging tow are incorporated leading to predictions of the ultimate strength of the bridging ligaments in mixed mode conditions. Given the traction law, which may be a material property, the fracture behaviour of a part can be predicted.

INTRODUCTION

Through-thickness reinforcement is a promising solution to the problem of delamination susceptibility in laminated composites, but its acceptance by the design community awaits dependable models of its performance and failure. Models have been slow in coming, mainly because the factors involved in the failure of through-thickness reinforcing elements and their interaction with the laminate through which they pass are, in the absence of close experimental observations, impossible to predict, and, even after the experiments have been done, dauntingly complex, at least at first sight.

Now at last experiments have been reported that show many of the essential details, with key elements of behaviour apparently being universal among bridging tows of various kinds, including stitches and short fibrous rods (so-called “z-fibers”). With substantial experimental basis, a view of the action and failure of stitches and short rods can be developed that is after all remarkably simple. A model of the response of the bridging tow to mixed mode loading

can be formulated and solved analytically, giving useful insight into the governing material and geometrical factors.

The material information required to analyze crack bridging effects in delamination is the relationship between the bridging tractions applied to the fracture surfaces by the bridging entities and the opening and sliding displacements of the bridged crack. For discrete bridging entities such as fiber tows, the bridging tractions can be represented by the tractions that would have to act on a section of the tow at the fracture plane if the tow was cut in two there and tractions applied to maintain the same stress state throughout the tow (Fig. 1). Let the traction vector be denoted $\mathbf{T} = (T_1, T_3)$ and the vector of total crack displacements be denoted $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, u_3)$ in the coordinate system of Fig. 1. The bridging traction law $\mathbf{T}[\mathbf{u}]$ or its inverse $\mathbf{u}[\mathbf{T}]$ is often a material property, independent of loading configuration and specimen geometry.

In many cases, the bridging tractions in discrete bridging entities can be conveniently and accurately replaced by spatially averaged tractions, \mathbf{t} , acting continuously over the fracture surface, which greatly simplifies subsequent bridged crack analysis. Such averaged tractions would be related to \mathbf{T} by the area fraction, c_t , occupied by the discrete bridging tows on the delamination plane, $\mathbf{t} = c_t \mathbf{T}$. But here the problem is taken no further than establishing $\mathbf{T}[\mathbf{u}]$ or $\mathbf{u}[\mathbf{T}]$.

Fig. 1: Bridging tractions and crack displacements.

OBSERVED MECHANISMS

Observations of damage during mode I, mode II, and mixed mode delamination cracking in end notch flexure, end notch cantilever, cantilever beam, and lap joint specimens have been reported in [1-6]; and during failure tests of small cuboidal specimens containing a single stitch under controlled shear displacement in [7]. The mechanisms seen in mode I and mode II are related: those in mode I appear to be a subset of those in mode II, as will be explained in the following. Thus the physics of the mixed mode problem can be introduced by considering the mode II case alone.

A representative schematic of the relation $T_1[u_1]$ from experiments on stitched laminates is shown in Fig. 2. Different mechanisms are observed at different values of the total crack sliding displacement. The following summary refers to both laminates stitched with glass or

Kevlar stitches and laminates reinforced with short carbon fibre rods, approximately 3 – 6 mm thick.

Ahead of the delamination crack tip in a typical stitched laminate, bridging tows are not visibly deformed or damaged [1,2]. No microcracking or debonding is observed. The tow debonds from the surrounding laminate when the delamination crack reaches it. Debond cracks are initially most pronounced on the side of the bridging tow where tensile normal stresses would be expected, but when $2u_1$ exceeds ~ 0.2 mm, the tows are debonded around their entire circumference over slip zones that have extended to either the surface of the laminate (stitches) or the end of the tow (short rods).

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Fig. 2: Schematic of shear tractions for mode II loading of a stitch, with dominant mechanisms listed.

At the smallest crack sliding displacements, the bridging tow deflects through plasticity, which consists of axial shear within the tow in a coordinate system aligned with the tow fiber direction. Even in bridging tows immediately behind the delamination crack tip, where $2u_1 \sim 10 \mu\text{m}$, polarized light microscopy reveals a well demarcated zone of crazing within the tow [3]. Beginning at displacements $2u_1 \sim 0.1$ mm, significant plasticity is also seen in the laminate; and later ($2u_1 > 0.6$ mm), splitting cracks and spalling are seen. At these higher sliding displacements, the damage within the bridging tow itself has matured into numerous axial matrix cracks parallel to the local fiber direction, separating it into strands which slide along one another to accommodate large axial shear strains. This process limits the magnitude of any bending moments developed in the tow.

The domain of traction-displacement data such as Fig. 2 that can be accounted for by matrix mediated plasticity alone is brief. For common aerospace fiber and resin systems, matrix damage leads to large strains at relatively low stresses: strains are $\sim 1\%$ at stresses above approximately 75 MPa, with hardening to at most ~ 100 MPa as the shear strain within the bridging tow approaches 10% [8,9,10]. Therefore, for the bridging tow to support shear

bridging tractions, T_1 , much above 100 MPa, it must bend near the fracture plane so that a significant load is carried by its fibers in tension. This transition occurs at relatively low sliding displacements, $2u_1 \sim 0.1 - 0.2$ mm at most. For $2u_1 > 0.2$ mm, the total load increases to ultimate failure when $2u_1 \approx 1$ mm and $T_1 \sim 1$ GPa [2,7]. Such a high load can only be sustained if the fibers in the stitch have rotated on the fracture plane through quite large angles.

Post-mortem failure of stitched laminates shows that large rotations have indeed occurred, but only near the fracture plane, where the bridging tow has ploughed laterally through the laminate and assumed a locus approximating a hyperbolic tangent (as in the schematic of Fig. 1). The total path length of this locus at peak load is much larger than could be expected if the bridging tow extended purely by elastic stretching. Much of the lateral ploughing and the crack displacement is evidently accommodated by axial sliding of the tow. In stitched laminates tested to stitch failure, pronounced dimples are left on the outer laminate surfaces where the surface segments of the stitch have been pulled in towards the fracture plane [7].

Peak load corresponds in stitched laminates to rupture of the stitch. In a laminate reinforced by short rods, peak load is usually associated with pullout of the rod. Pullout could be preceded by rupture of the rod, depending on the rod dimensions and other factors. For either type of reinforcement, there is a dramatic drop in load after peak load followed by some relatively small but enduring pullout forces.

Because debonding and plasticity within the bridging tow begin very close to the delamination crack tip, there is no appreciable interval of crack sliding displacement where deformation is purely elastic. The stiffness of the bridging system expected for an elastic, undamaged tow and laminate in the presence of a delamination crack is relatively high – of the same order as the shear modulus of the composite. On the scale of Fig. 2, the line representing such an elastic response will be almost coincident with the ordinate. The first significant departure from the ordinate heralds the onset of plasticity within the bridging tow and possibly debonding.

MODEL FORMULATION AND SOLUTION

Here the formulation presented in [11] is generalised to mixed mode loading with mode II displacements in the direction x_1 . The problem of the deforming bridging tow will be idealized by the following assumptions, *with reference to the nomenclature shown in Fig. 3*.

1. The bridging tow will be assumed to deform internally in shear as a rigid/perfectly plastic material. The shear flow stress will be denoted τ_0 .
2. The bridging tow debonds from the laminate over a zone that propagates a distance l_s from the fracture plane that is large compared to the tow diameter. Axial sliding of the tow relative to the laminate is opposed by friction, which is assumed to be characterized by a uniform shear traction, τ .
3. Elastic deformation of the laminate in the z -direction is assumed to contribute negligibly to the displacement of the bridging tow at the fracture plane.
4. All strains in the bridging tow are assumed to be either axial extension or axial shear that is uniform in (x_1, x_2) , i.e., planes initially normal to the x_3 -axis remain so. Bending effects are ignored since axial splitting cracks separate the tow into thin segments, which slide over one another without accumulating significant bending moments.

5. Lateral ploughing of the bridging tow through the laminate (in the x_1 -direction) is assumed to follow the mechanics of a punch being pushed into a rigid/perfectly plastic medium in plane strain [11]. Thus the tow's deflection is opposed by hydrostatic compression, σ_h , acting on its width, D , projected on a plane normal to the direction of deflection. The magnitude of σ_h is assumed to be independent of the lateral displacement of the tow and uniform along that portion of the tow where nonzero lateral displacement has occurred (which turns out to be a domain that does not extend far from the delamination fracture plane) and zero elsewhere.

The state of the bridging tow will be described in terms of two variables only, the displacements $\xi(x_3)$ and $\zeta(x_3)$ in the directions x_1 and x_3 respectively of a slice of the tow lying between x_3 and x_3+dx_3 . While the slice does not rotate (i.e., planes normal to the direction x_3 remain so), the fibers within it rotate as the tow deflects in shear. The axial strain, ε , and the rotation of the fibers (or the angle of deflection of the tow), θ , are given by

$$\varepsilon = \left[\left(\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_3} \right)^2 + \left(1 + \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial x_3} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} - 1 \quad (1a)$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x_3} / \left(1 + \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial x_3} \right) \right] \quad (1b)$$

The axial stress in the tow, σ_t , i.e., the stress component in the local fiber direction, is

$$\sigma_t = \varepsilon E_t \approx \varepsilon V_f E_f \quad (2)$$

where E_t is the axial Young's modulus of the bridging tow, E_f that of its fibers, and V_f the volume fraction of the fibers within it. Force equilibrium between the axial stress and the friction stress leads in the shear lag approximation (large l_s) to the familiar result

$$\sigma_t = \sigma_0 - 2\tau \frac{x_3}{R} \quad (x_3 < l_s, \quad l_s = R\sigma_0/2\tau) \quad (3)$$

where σ_0 is the value of σ_t on the fracture plane ($x_3 = 0$), l_s is the slip length over which frictionally constrained sliding occurs, and $R \equiv 2A_t/s$, with s the circumference of the tow and A_t its cross-sectional area. For a bridging tow of circular cross-section, R is its radius.

The other equation of equilibrium for the bridging tow balances the lateral force generated by the axial stress in the tow in concert with its curvature against the resistance of the laminate. Denote by $\mathbf{F}(x_3)$ the axial force resultant in the tow ($|\mathbf{F}| = \sigma_t A_t$; \mathbf{F} oriented along the tow) and by \mathbf{P} the force of resistance of the laminate per unit length of the tow:

$$|\mathbf{P}| = D\sigma_h \quad (4a)$$

Force balance for a slice of the tow between x_3 and $x_3 + dx_3$ requires

$$\mathbf{F}(x_3 + dx_3) - \mathbf{F}(x_3) + \mathbf{P}dx_3 = 0 \quad (4b)$$

In evaluating the difference $\mathbf{F}(x_3 + dx_3) - \mathbf{F}(x_3)$ on the left hand side, account must be taken of variations in the magnitude of F with x_3 as well as in the direction in which \mathbf{F} acts, because the tow has curvature (variation in θ with x_3). For simplicity, the component P_1 of \mathbf{P} in the x_1 -direction is assumed to be its only nonzero component and only leading order terms in θ are retained [11]. Substituting (3) into (4b) yields for equilibrium in the x_1 -direction

$$\left[\sigma_0 - \frac{2\tau x_3}{R} \right] \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x_3} = -P_1 \quad . \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) is to be solved for $\theta(x_3)$ and σ_0 subject to boundary conditions yet to be specified.

Given $\theta(x_3)$ and σ_0 (and thence $\sigma_t(x_3)$ via Eq. (3)), the displacement fields, $\xi(x_3)$ and $\zeta(x_3)$, and thence the crack displacements, u_1 and u_3 , follow from Eq. (1) (see [11]):

$$u_1 = \xi(0) \quad \xi(x_3) = \int_{x_0}^{x_3} \left[\frac{\sigma_s(x'_3) \sin \theta}{E_s} + \sin \theta \right] dx'_3 \quad (6a)$$

$$u_3 = \zeta(0) \quad \zeta(x_3) = \int_{l_s}^{x_3} \left[\frac{\sigma_s(x'_3) \cos \theta}{E_s} + \cos \theta - 1 \right] dx'_3. \quad (6b)$$

For the displacement, ξ , in the x_1 -direction, nonzero contributions to the integral arise only where the tow has deflected. The boundary of the domain of deflection and therefore of the integration in Eq. (6a) is denoted x_0 . The lower limit of integration in Eq. (6b) corresponds to the end of the debond/slip zone, $x_3 = l_s$, where ζ also vanishes.

Specifying \mathbf{T} provides the following boundary conditions for the system of model equations [11,12]. It is convenient to preserve the simplest possible relation between (T_1, T_3) and (t_1, t_3) , namely $t_i = c_t T_i$ ($i = 1,3$) where c_t is the area fraction constituted by the tows on the delamination fracture plane *when the tows are in their undeformed state*. This is achieved by defining T_1 and T_3 as those tractions that will satisfy equilibrium in Fig. 1 if they are supposed to act over the original cross-sectional area of the tow, A_t , rather than the area of the deformed tow on the fracture plane, which is $A_t/\cos\theta_0$, where $\theta_0 = \theta(0)$. Then equilibrium on an imaginary cut across the bridging tow at $x_3 = 0$ yields [11,12]

$$T_1 \approx \sin \theta_0 \sigma_0 + \tau_0 \quad (7a)$$

and

$$T_3 = \cos \theta_0 \sigma_0 - 2 \sin \theta_0 \tau_0 \quad . \quad (7b)$$

This boundary condition is the only place where the shear flow stress of the stitch, τ_0 , appears in the problem. When $\theta_0 \approx 0$, at the onset of displacement, $T_1 \approx \tau_0$; the shear flow stress in the stitch must be exceeded for deflection to occur. At large displacements (large θ_0), the axial stress, σ_0 , grows increasingly dominant.

The system of model equations can be solved analytically to yield the following expressions for the crack displacements [11,12]

$$u_3 \approx \frac{\sigma_0^2}{2E_t\tau} - \frac{\sigma_0 \sin^{-1} \left[\frac{T_1 - \tau_0}{\sigma_0} \right] - (T_1 - \tau_0)}{P_x/s} \quad (8a)$$

and

$$u_1 \approx \frac{\sigma_0}{P_x/s} \left[1 - \sqrt{1 - \frac{(T_1 - \tau_0)^2}{\sigma_0^2}} \right] \quad (8b)$$

In Eq. (8a), the first term on the right hand side states the contribution from elastic stretching of the bridging tow, which, with the convention that $u_3 > 0$ when the crack opens, is a positive quantity; while the second term arises from the increase in path length accompanying the tow's deflection and is negative. The sliding displacement, u_1 , has the same sign as the bridging shear traction, T_1 .

Equation (8) may be rewritten in terms of the traction components, T_1 and T_3 , by substituting the following expression for the angle of deflection at the fracture plane [11]:

$$\theta_0 = \sin^{-1} \left[\frac{T_1 - \tau_0}{\sigma_0} \right] \quad (9)$$

and eliminating the axial stress in the rod at the fracture plane, σ_0 , via Eq. (7b). The resulting equations are transcendental but easily solved.

Quantitative predictions require values for the parameters E_t , R , τ , τ_0 , and P_1 . The first two come easily from the specifications of the bridging tow. Pullout tests will yield a value for τ , with $\tau \sim 10$ MPa for large tows in common aerospace resins. The flow stress, τ_0 , can be deduced from tests on laminates, with $\tau_0 \approx 100$ MPa for aerospace resins. The punch stress, P_1 , is related to the crush strength, σ_c , of the laminate by $P_1/D = 3\sigma_c$, implying $P_1/D \approx 900 - 1200$ MPa for typical aerospace laminates. Further details are to be found in [11].

Illustration for Mode II

The traction law for mode II displacements, $T_1[u_1]$, is obtained by imposing the constraint $u_3 = 0$. With the typical values for parameters listed above, there results the law depicted in Fig. 3. An experimental measurement of the same law is shown for comparison, taken from direct tests on small cuboidal specimens containing a single bridging stitch [2,7]. The agreement is very satisfactory. Several other crude predictions are also shown in Fig. 3. If the bridging stitch is assumed to accommodate sliding crack displacements by following the stepped path shown in the inset in Fig. 3 while stretching elastically along its length (a model suggested in [13]), the linear curve marked "elastic rope" is predicted. This line is about seven times steeper than the experimental curve, a severe consequence of ignoring the contribution to u_1 of

the lateral ploughing of the stitch through the laminate. If the bridging tow and laminate are replaced by a homogeneous elastic/perfectly plastic medium, the predicted curve is simply a constant stress at the flow stress, τ_0 . This severely underestimates the bridging traction, because it misses the contribution to the traction of the axial stress carried by the fibers in the tow, which rises as the fibers rotate and becomes dominant at quite low displacements. Thus quantitative comparison with a measured traction law suggests that the simple analytical model presented here captures the essential mechanisms.

Fig. 3: Comparison of various predictions of the traction law for a stitch bridging a mode II delamination crack with a direct experimental measurement due to Turrettini [7].

ULTIMATE FAILURE

As stated above, the model assumes that there is no limit to the slip length, l_s , but limits do indeed exist. If the bridging tow is a short rod, then when slip reaches its end, the rod will begin to pull out of the laminate, leading to ultimate failure of the bridging effect. This condition is easily incorporated in the model: it is simply $l_s = l_r$, where l_r is the half length of the rod. In a stitched laminate, the slip zone will reach the free surface of the laminate. When this happens, the surface segments of the stitch will be drawn down into the laminate, allowing further sliding of the stitch along its axis. This effect can be incorporated in the model by imposing a boundary condition on the axial displacement of the stitch at the surface of the laminate. Since the drawing down of the surface segment of the stitch is analogous to the lateral deflection of the stitch at the delamination fracture plane during mode II cracking, the boundary condition can be deduced from solutions for the mode II traction law [11]. The resulting problem is a minor modification of the problem stated here. The boundary condition at the end of the slip zone is the sole distinction in the model between stitching and reinforcement by fibrous rods.

The bridging tow, whether a fibrous rod or a stitch, can also fail by rupture if the axial tension in it is high enough. Tensile rupture can be incorporated in the model by imposing the

condition $\sigma_t \leq \sigma_{ult}$, where σ_{ult} is the tensile strength of the tow, which generally must be measured in a calibrating experiment.

Full details of failure in mixed mode conditions will be presented in [12].

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